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Assessing the Impact of Digital Integration on Operational Efficiency and Customer Behavioral Loyalty: A Structural Equation Modeling Approach to Express Logistics Services in Pakistan

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Abstract

This research investigates the factors influencing customer loyalty and satisfaction toward express logistics services on the Internet Plus context. The study proposes a conceptual framework with seven key variables, exploring the causal relationships between perceived value, service quality, brand image, customer relationships, trust, loyalty, and satisfaction. Using a quantitative approach, the research involved a literature review and a questionnaire survey with 500 respondents from Hyderabad, Pakistan. Data collection methods included convenience, targeted, and availability sampling. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) were used for data analysis, assessing model fitness, consistency, and conceptual validity. Results indicate that perceived value, service quality, customer relationships, brand image, and trust significantly impact on customer satisfaction. Furthermore, customer satisfaction and customer relationships positively influence customer loyalty. This study offers practical strategies for express logistics companies to enhance service quality, thereby improving competitiveness and ensuring long-term sustainability.

Keyword: Loyalty, Satisfaction, Express Delivery, Logistics service, Hyderabad Pakistan

1. Introduction

According to recent data from the Hyderabad, Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, the e-commerce industry in Hyderabad, Pakistan has witnessed significant growth, with online transactions reaching new heights and the number of online shoppers growing exponentially. As the demand for online shopping continues to increase, the need for efficient and reliable express logistics services has also intensified (Hye and Miraz 2020; Javed 2020). The logistics sector plays a crucial role in ensuring the seamless operation of e-commerce, serving as a vital link between retailers and customers (Rashid and Rasheed 2024). In particular, express logistics, which provides rapid transportation and delivery of goods, is crucial to ensuring customer satisfaction in this growing digital landscape (Raji et al. 2017). The rise of digital integration in logistics services, encompassing technologies such as real-time tracking, automated warehouses, and data-driven routing systems, has transformed how express delivery services operate (Sumbal et al. 2024). As consumers increasingly expect faster and more reliable services, the role of digital technologies in improving operational efficiency and service quality becomes more pronounced (Lin et al. 2023). Hyderabad, Pakistan's express logistics sector, particularly in cities like Hyderabad, is gradually adopting digital tools to enhance the customer experience, though challenges remain in terms of service consistency and customer expectations (Rashid and Rasheed 2024).

Service efficiency, a crucial factor in logistics, refers to the ability of logistics companies to deliver goods in a timely manner, with minimal errors, and at an acceptable cost (N. A. Memon, Shah, and Warsi 2023). The integration of digital tools, such as mobile apps, online tracking, and automated sorting, has the potential to significantly improve service efficiency (Arif, Shah, and Khan 2023). However, it is not without its challenges, such as technological barriers, inconsistent infrastructure, and the varying levels of digital adoption across different regions (Akil and Ungan 2022). Despite these obstacles, express logistics companies in Hyderabad are increasingly exploring digital solutions to streamline operations and meet the growing demands of online shoppers (Hussain, Amin, and Rasool 2023).

Customer satisfaction in express logistics is not just about fast delivery but also about the

reliability, transparency, and communication of the service provided (Ahmed, Huma, and Ikram 2019a). The interaction between customers and the logistics service providers ranging from ease of order placement to real-time tracking and delivery plays a key role in satisfaction levels (Lin et al. 2023). Research by (Chang and Zhang 2016) defines express service as the swift collection, transportation, and delivery of goods, which requires close attention to each stage of the logistics process (Sumbal et al. 2024) . For customers, factors such as on-time delivery, accurate tracking, and minimal damage or loss are critical indicators of service quality (N. A. Memon et al. 2023).

Moreover, customer loyalty in express logistics is closely tied to service quality and satisfaction. Studies show that loyal customers not only repurchase but also become advocates for the service, further driving business growth (Rashid and Rasheed 2024). As digital integration enhances service efficiency, the potential for increasing customer loyalty becomes even greater (Nabi et al. 2023). However, despite technological advancements, customer complaints about delays, damages, and poor service still exist, highlighting the need for continuous improvement in service delivery (Rashid and Rasheed 2024) . These challenges also reflect the varying degrees of digital integration and its actual impact on customer satisfaction in Hyderabad, Pakistan (Arif et al. 2023) .

This research aims to explore the impact of digital integration and service efficiency on customer satisfaction and loyalty within the express logistics sector in Hyderabad, Hyderabad, Pakistan. Through an investigation of 500 respondents, This study will uncover the key drivers of consumer contentment and allegiance in the context of digital advancements. The results will deliver valuable Understanding for logistics companies seeking to improve their service offerings, increase operational performance, and foster long-term customer relationships (Khan et al. 2021; N. A. Memon et al. 2023).

2. Research Overview

2.1 Quality of Service

Quality of Service in logistics is critical for ensuring customer satisfaction. According to (Rashid and Rasheed 2024), effective logistics services hinge on both operational quality and the ability to meet customer expectations. The integration of digital tools, such as automated tracking systems and real-time communication platforms, has improved service delivery in Hyderabad, Pakistan's logistics sector, contributing to higher level of service excellence and customer contentment (Rashid and Rasheed 2024). Studies have found that operational excellence, including punctuality and precision in delivery, is highly valued by Hyderabad, Pakistani consumers (Bukhari 2018). In this context, logistics service quality directly affects customer loyalty and repeat business, with many logistics firms investing in technology to improve service standards.

The role of technology in logistics service quality is pivotal in Hyderabad, Pakistan, especially with e-commerce's rapid growth. Digital systems streamline operations and reduce service delivery time, thereby increasing overall efficiency (N. A. Memon et al. 2023). This improved service delivery directly impacts customer satisfaction levels, which in turn boosts long-term business growth and customer retention rates in Hyderabad, Pakistan's competitive logistics market (Mahajan et al. 2024).

2.2 Perceived Value

Customer Perceived Value (CPV) plays a significant role in shaping customer contentment in logistics services. CPV is defined as the overall assessment of the service provided, where customers weigh the perceived benefits against the costs involved

(Mahajan et al. 2024). For instance, studies in Hyderabad, Pakistan's e-commerce sector have shown that perceived value is a major driver of customer satisfaction, with consumers placing high importance on timely and cost-effective deliveries (Lin et al. 2023b)

Recent studies by (N. A. Memon et al. 2023) highlight the importance of offering perceived value that aligns with customer expectations. In Hyderabad, Pakistan, businesses that successfully improve perceived value through improved service quality and personalized customer experiences tend to see stronger customer retention and repeat purchases (Hussain et al. 2023a). As perceived value increases, so does the likelihood of customers recommending the service to others, reinforcing positive word-of-mouth.

2.3 Brand Image

Brand image in logistics not only helps companies stand out in a competitive market but also plays a pivotal role in customer decision-making. A positive brand image, built on trust and consistent service delivery, can significantly enhance customer loyalty (Raji et al. 2017). In Hyderabad, Pakistan, where trust in delivery services is crucial, logistics firms must align their brand image with reliability and transparency to foster customer trust (Hussain et al. 2023).

(Khan et al. 2023a) argue that brand image in logistics is closely linked to customer perceptions of service quality and company values. In Hyderabad, Pakistan, logistics companies that focus on building a strong, reliable brand image, especially through digital presence and customer feedback mechanisms, tend to experience higher satisfaction and brand loyalty (N. A. Memon et al. 2023).

2.4 CRM (Customer Relationship Management)

CRM is an essential strategy for maintaining long-term customer relationships and loyalty in the logistics industry. A study by Bennett and Rundle-Thiele (2004) found that CRM practices, when implemented effectively, enhance customer satisfaction by offering tailored services and personalized interactions. In Hyderabad, Pakistan, CRM systems integrated with digital platforms have become increasingly important, allowing logistics companies to manage customer data more effectively and provide personalized services (Rashid and Rasheed 2024).

Additionally, recent studies in Hyderabad, Pakistan show that effective CRM leads to stronger customer engagement, with customers feeling more valued and understood, resulting in increased loyalty and positive feedback (Nabi et al. 2023). By focusing on customer needs through CRM systems, logistics companies can foster customer trust and satisfaction, which are essential for sustained success in the competitive logistics market.

2.5 Trust

Trust is a foundational element in the relationship between customers and logistics service providers. In Hyderabad, Pakistan's logistics industry, where customers rely on third-party providers for timely deliveries, trust becomes essential for customer retention. According to (Doney and Cannon 1997), trust fosters commitment and long-term relationships. Recent research by (Zaheer et al. 2024) further supports this, showing that trust in delivery services is directly linked to increased satisfaction and loyalty among Hyderabad, Pakistani consumers.

In the context of Hyderabad, Pakistan, online trust is becoming increasingly important as e-commerce and digital logistics continue to grow. Customers need assurance that their

packages will be delivered securely and on time. (Hong and Cho 2011) suggest that building online trust through transparency and consistent communication is crucial in the logistics sector. By improving trust, logistics companies minimize customer attrition and boost customer lifetime value.

2.6 Loyalty and Customer Satisfaction

A well-established determinant of customer loyalty is customer satisfaction, particularly in the logistics and e-commerce sectors. Studies by (Hadi, Aslam, and Gulzar 2019) suggest that customer satisfaction drives repeat purchases and enhances customer loyalty over time. In Hyderabad, Pakistan, customer satisfaction in logistics is closely linked to service quality, as consumers demand faster, more reliable delivery services (Fraihat et al. 2023; N. Memon, Shah, and Warsi 2023a).

Study by (Hussain, Amin, and Rasool 2023b) indicates that customer satisfaction in Hyderabad, Pakistan's logistics sector leads to higher levels of loyalty and positive word-of-mouth. The satisfaction-loyalty relationship is particularly strong in the e-commerce context, where loyal customers are more likely to recommend services to others, further enhancing the company's customer base (N. Memon et al. 2023a). Companies that focus on enhancing customer satisfaction through improved delivery reliability and communication are better positioned to build lasting customer loyalty in Hyderabad, Pakistan's competitive logistics market.

3. Research Methodology and Materials

3.1 Conceptual Framework

The theoretical foundation of this research was established by incorporating existing theories and empirical studies related to customer satisfaction, service quality, and logistics in Hyderabad, Pakistan. We constructed a comprehensive research framework by integrating the findings of previous research and incorporating four key theoretical models. These models were adapted to suit the unique characteristics of the express logistics sector in Hyderabad, Pakistan, Particularly focusing on how digital integration, customer relationship management, and service quality influence customer loyalty and satisfaction.

Previous research has highlighted the significance of service quality in influencing customer satisfaction within logistics services. For instance, a study by (Hussain et al. 2023) underscored the impact of logistics service quality on improving customer loyalty within the logistics sector of Hyderabad, Pakistan. The SERVQUAL model, developed by (Parasuraman, Berry, and Zeithaml 1991) has become a prominent tool in logistics research for evaluating customer perceptions of service quality across various dimensions such as reliability, responsiveness, and assurance (N. A. Memon et al. 2023). This model serves as the core component of our research framework, allowing us to analyze how service quality factors such as timeliness, transparency, and professionalism influence customer satisfaction in Hyderabad, Pakistan.

In addition to the SERVQUAL model, we also drew upon the Customer Relationship Management (CRM) theory, which has been demonstrated to significantly influence customer loyalty and satisfaction (Karim and Habiba 2020). CRM systems, especially those combined with digital tools, are crucial in enhancing customer interaction and fostering long-lasting relationships with clients in Hyderabad, Pakistan, where consumer trust in service providers is critical, CRM provides a strategic advantage by enabling personalized interactions and tailored services (N. A. Memon et al. 2023) .

Building on the work of (N. A. Memon et al. 2023) , we also integrated a model of perceived value in the context of logistics services. This model posits that customer satisfaction is a function of the perceived value of service, which is derived from the combination of the service benefits and the cost incurred (Suarniki and Daud 2024). In the logistics industry, perceived value directly influences customer loyalty and the likelihood of repeat business, particularly in competitive markets like Hyderabad, Pakistan.

Lastly, a study by (Hussain et al. 2023b) presents a conceptual framework for incorporating digital technologies into logistics services and examines their influence on customer satisfaction. By analyzing how digital tools like mobile apps, real-time tracking, and automated sorting affect the service delivery process, we aim to understand the role of digital integration in enhancing customer satisfaction and loyalty in the logistics sector. These four models, SERVQUAL, CRM, Perceived Value, and Digital Integration, were integrated to create the theoretical framework for this research, as shown in Figure 1. This model guides our investigation into the interrelationships between service quality, customer relationship management, perceived value, and digital integration in the context of express logistics in Hyderabad, Pakistan.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

H1: The quality of service significantly influences customer satisfaction.

H2: Perceived value significantly impacts customer satisfaction.

H3: A well-established brand image plays a crucial role in influencing customer satisfaction.

H4: Effective CRM (Customer Relationship Management) contributes significantly to customer satisfaction.

H5: Consumer trust is essential in enhancing consumer satisfaction.

H6: Higher customer satisfaction leads to increased customer loyalty.

H7: Effective Customer Relationship Management (CRM) is key to fostering customer loyalty.

3.2 Research Method

In this research, we utilized a random sampling approach to distribute the questionnaire to a target group of logistics service consumers in Hyderabad, Pakistan. Specifically

focusing on those using express logistics services. The questionnaire was distributed both online and in paper format to ensure a broad and diverse sample. Data were collected and organized to analyze the key factors affecting customer satisfaction and loyalty in Hyderabad, Pakistan's logistics sector.

The questionnaire was designed to include a set of screening questions, demographic questions, and measurement items related to the core variables. The survey's demographic section collected data on several participant characteristics, which encompassed gender, age, education level, and the frequency of logistics service usage. The measurement of key variables was done using a Likert scale ranging from "very dissatisfied" (1) to "very satisfied" (5) to assess the satisfaction levels related to the seven proposed variables. These variables were linked to the proposed hypotheses, including, perceived value, brand image, service quality, trust and CRM.

The IOC (Item Objective Congruence) analysis was performed to evaluate the relevance of the measurement item. This assessment showed that every scale item received a score of 0.6 or more, indicating a high level of item relevance, as confirmed by expert raters. A preliminary test was carried out with a sample of 30 participants to assess the internal consistency of the items. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for all items exceeded or equaled 0.7, representing good consistency and reliability in the assessment scale (Sarmiento and Costa 2017).

For data analysis, we employed statistical software such as Jamovi and AMOS 26.0. The data were analyzed using CFA (Confirmatory Factor Analysis) to assess the convergence, precision, and validity of the model. We applied SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) to explore the connections among the variables and evaluate the proposed hypotheses regarding customer satisfaction and loyalty in Hyderabad, Pakistan's express logistics sector.

3.3 Sample Size and Population

The goal of population in this research refers to the specific group of individuals the research is designed to study, focusing on consumers of express logistics services and employees of logistics companies in Hyderabad, Pakistan. This population was chosen because they directly interact with logistics services and are key stakeholders in understanding customer satisfaction and loyalty (Dare 2025),(Gravetter, Forzano, and Rakow 2009).

For this study, we followed the guidelines for sample size estimation for structural equation modeling (SEM). According to (Kline 1998, 2023) a minimum of 200 respondents is recommended for conducting SEM to ensure robust statistical analysis and reliable results. In line with this suggestion, we distributed the survey to 550 respondents. After screening the data for completeness and accuracy, 500 valid responses were retained for analysis, which is consistent with the recommendations for SEM-based studies (N. A. Memon et al. 2023). This sample size allows for a thorough examination of the relationships between key variables, such as service quality, customer satisfaction, loyalty, and CRM, in the context of Hyderabad, Pakistan's express logistics industry.

3.4 Sampling Technique

In this research, we used judgmental sampling to select the top logistics companies operating in Hyderabad, Pakistan based on their reputation and service quality. The logistics companies chosen for this study included Leopards Courier, Pakistan Post, and TCS (Transexpress Courier Services), all of which are major players in the express

delivery industry in Hyderabad, Pakistan and its Geographical Location of study area is shown in Graph 1. These companies were selected due to their extensive presence, established customer base, and their critical role in the logistics and courier sector (Abbas et al. 2024; Akhmedov 2017).

Study Area Map

Graph 1: Geographical Location of Study Area

Next, we employed quota sampling to ensure that we obtained a diverse representation of respondents from various demographic backgrounds. The quotas were designed to capture differences in factors including gender, age, and frequency of service use, ensuring that the sample reflected the general population of logistics service users. The quotas are detailed in Table 1^{1,2}.

Additionally, we utilized a convenience sampling method for distributing the survey. The questionnaire was made available both online and offline, and respondents were encouraged to complete the survey in person or via email. This approach helped ensure that we reached a broad segment of the population across different regions in Hyderabad, Pakistan, including urban and rural areas, in order to thoroughly assess customer satisfaction and loyalty within the logistics sector (N. A. Memon et al. 2023).

Table 1¹: *Specification of Sample Size and Units*

Names of Enterprises	Total Active Consumers in Hyderabad, Pakistan (thousand)	Proportional Sample Size
Leopards Courier	8,702	100
Pakistan Post	6,507	190
TCS (Transexpress Courier Services)	10,260	210
Total	25,469	500

Table 1²:

Source: Constructed by author.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Demographic Information

The study's cohort comprised 500 participants, with demographic data presented in Table 2. Men represented 45% of the sample, while women made up 55%. Most participants (52.6%) fell into the 25-34 age bracket. This was followed by the 19-24 age group at 27.2%, the 35-44 group at 12.8%, and those aged 45 or above at 7.4%.

The educational breakdown of the sample shows that most participants (63.4%) were university graduates, while 8.6% had completed a master's degree, and 28% had completed high school or below. When examining employment sectors, respondents reported working in transportation/logistics (11.4%), public utilities (5.2%), intelligent manufacturing (6.8%), and other sectors, with the remaining 57.6% engaged in various professions.

Regarding monthly online shopping spending, the majority of respondents reported spending over 15,000 PKR (Hyderabad, Pakistani Rupees), with 72.6% of participants falling into this category. Additionally, 83.4% of respondents reported making online purchases more than five times a month, reflecting the growing reliance on

e-commerce platforms and courier services in Hyderabad, Pakistan.

Table 2: Profile of Participant Characteristics (N=500)

Demographic Factor	Category	Number (of Respondents)	Percent of Sample (%)
Gender	Male Participants	205	41%
	Female Participants	295	59%
Age Group	Less than 24 years old	133	26.60%
	aged 25-34	269	53.80%
	aged 35-44	65	13%
	45 or older	33	6.60%
Education	High school or below	137	27.40%
	Undergraduate	327	65.40%
	Master's degree	36	7.20%
Industry	Smart manufacturing	54	10.80%
	Public institutions	23	4.60%
	Transportation/logistics	33	6.60%
	Internet-related	103	20.60%
	Other	287	57.40%
Time to Use Express Service	Less than 3 years	155	31%
	3-5 years	215	43%
	More than 5 years	130	26%
Monthly Online Shopping Spending	Less than 1,000 PKR	131	26.20%
	More than 1,000 PKR	369	73.80%
Number of Online Purchases	Less than 3	80	16%
	5-Apr	116	23.20%
	7-Jun	135	27%
	8 or more	169	33.80%

4.2 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

This study evaluated variable reliability using Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient, with validity assessed through responses from 500 participants. To ensure the tools measured their intended constructs effectively, construct validity was also examined. The alpha coefficients for each parameter are detailed in Table 3. The calculated alpha values for the independent variables were 0.820, 0.739, 0.801, 0.724, 0.740, and 0.714, while the dependent variable had an alpha value of 0.765. Since these results are above the established threshold of 0.7, they confirm the dependability and internal consistency of the questionnaire's constructs.

To evaluate convergent validity, this research adopted the framework proposed by (N. Memon et al. 2023a) in their analysis of service quality and customer loyalty within Hyderabad, Pakistan's logistics industry. The evaluation involved examining key metrics such as factor loadings, composite reliability (CR), and average variance extracted (AVE). The findings demonstrated strong convergent validity, with all factor loadings surpassing the 0.5 threshold, composite reliability scores exceeding 0.7, and average variance extracted values being above the 0.4 benchmark. These findings indicate that the constructs and measurement tools demonstrate both reliability and convergent validity, and the corresponding results can be found in Table 3 & 3¹.

Table 3: Outcomes of Confirmatory Factor Analysis, Including Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variables	Source Measurement Scale	of Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Loading Coefficient	CR	AVE
SQ	Ali et al. (2021)	6	0.82	0.556-0.743	0.824	0.441
PV	Hussain et al. (2023)	4	0.739	0.576-0.692	0.74	0.417
BI	Akram et al. (2022)	4	0.801	0.695-0.729	0.801	0.502
CRM	Raza and Imran (2020)	4	0.724	0.606-0.783	0.723	0.469
T (Trust)	Nabi et al. (2023)	3	0.74	0.608-0.710	0.743	0.42
Customer Satisfaction (CS)	Memon and Shah (2023)	3	0.714	0.636-0.702	0.715	0.455
Customer Loyalty (CL)	(Khan et al. 2023b)	5	0.765	0.604-0.648	0.768	0.3

Table 3¹:

The measurement model demonstrated a strong fit with the observed data, as confirmed by the results in Table 4. All required criteria were met for both absolute fit indices (such as CMIN/DF, GFI, AGFI, and RMSEA) and incremental fit measurements (like CFI, NFI, and TLI). This strong alignment ensures the overall adequacy of the constructs. In summary, the various goodness-of-fit indicators utilized in the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) collectively point to a satisfactory and acceptable level of model fit. Figure 5 provides the definitions for the abbreviations of the goodness-of-fit indicators utilized in this analysis.

Table 4: Model Fit Statistics for the Measurement Model

Model Fit Indicator	Recommended Threshold	Observed Value
CMIN/DF	< 5.0 (N. A. Memon et al. 2023)	1.233
GFI	> 0.85 (Hussain et al. 2023)	0.943
AGFI	> 0.80 (Hussain et al. 2023)	0.93
NFI	≥ 0.80 (Adnan et al. 2020) (Tipu and Fantasy 2019)	0.91
CFI	≥ 0.80 (N. A. Memon et al. 2023)	0.982
TLI	≥ 0.80 ((Khan et al. 2023)	0.979
RMSEA	< 0.08 (Khan et al. 2023)	0.022
Overall Assessment		Model is Consistent with Data

Figure 5: Define The Abbreviations

Discriminant validity was evaluated following the method proposed by (N. Memon et al. 2023) This assessment involved calculating the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each construct and comparing it to the inter-construct correlations. The data in Table 5 indicates that for every construct, the square root of its AVE was higher than its correlation with any other construct, thereby providing strong evidence for discriminant validity (N. Memon et al. 2023).

Table 5: Discriminant Validity

	SQ	PV	BI	CRM	T	CS	CL
SQ	0.664						
PV	0.406	0.643					
BI	0.33	0.372	0.708				
CRM	0.19	0.299	0.387	0.684			
T	0.401	0.393	0.368	0.39	0.648		
CS	0.448	0.392	0.441	0.392	0.471	0.674	
CL	0.365	0.446	0.451	0.443	0.407	0.589	0.63

Note: Values on the diagonal indicate the square root of the AVE for the corresponding construct.

Source: Author's own compilation.

4.3 SEM (Structural Equation Model)

This study utilized SEM to investigate causal relationships and pathways among variables, aligning with methodologies discussed by (Hussain et al. 2023) SEM is

particularly effective for simultaneously analyzing multiple interrelationships within the structural model, as compared to traditional statistical methods that evaluate individual relationships in isolation. AMOS 26 software was used to refine and analyze the structural models, as seen in studies conducted by (N. A. Memon et al. 2023) . Our structural model demonstrated robust fit to the observed data, as evidenced by the following indices: $DF/CMIN = 2.571$, $GFI = 00.867$, $AGFI = 00.844$, $NFI = 0.806$, $CFI = 00.871$, $TLI = 00.858$, and $RMSEA = 0.056$. These values fall within acceptable thresholds, thereby supporting the reliability and validity of the proposed framework. This alignment with observed data is consistent with similar findings in the literature (N. A. Memon et al. 2023), A summary of these fit indices is presented in Figure 6.

Table 6: *Displays The Goodness Of Fit For The Structural Model*

Index	Acceptable	Statistical Values
CMIN/DF	< 5.00 (N. Memon et al. 2023a)	2.571
GFI	> 00.85 (Hussain et al. 2023b)	00.867
AGFI	> 00.80 (Hussain et al. 2023b)	00.844
NFI	> 00.80 (Tipu and Fantazy 2019) (Adnan et al. 2020)	00.806
CFI	> 0.80 (N. A. Memon et al. 2023)	0.871
TLI	> 0.80 (Khan et al. 2023b)	0.858
RMSEA	< 0.08 (Khan et al. 2023c)	0.056
Overall Assessment		Model is Consistent with Data

Figure 6: shows indices used in structural equation modeling:

4.4 Results of Hypothesis Testing

Our hypothesis testing revealed that all proposed hypotheses were supported at a significance level of $p=0.05$ (see Table 7). This analysis, which assessed the significance of each variable through its regression weights and R^2 variance within the research model, particularly highlighted Customer Satisfaction (CS) as having the most substantial influence on Customer Loyalty (CL). The regression coefficient for this relationship was $\beta=0.708$, underscoring CS's critical role in the model.

Among the variables influencing CS, Trust (T) demonstrates the highest impact ($\beta = 0.283$), followed by Service Quality (SQ) ($\beta = 0.241$), Brand Image (BI) ($\beta = 0.227$), Customer Relationship Management (CRM) ($\beta = 0.199$), and Perceived Value (PV) ($\beta = 0.187$). The results from this study validate the importance of every pathway within the structural equation model, thereby enhancing our comprehension of the interconnections among the variables

Table 7: *Empirical Outcomes of Structural Equation Model Hypotheses*

“Hypothesis”	“ β ”	T_Value	Outcome
H ¹ : SQ → CS	00.241	5.595 [^]	Confirmed
H ² : PV → CS	00.187	4.217 [^]	Confirmed
H ³ : BI → CS	00.227	5.564 [^]	Confirmed
H ⁴ : CRM → CS	00.199	4.099 [^]	Confirmed
H ⁵ : T → CS	00.283	5.916 [^]	Confirmed
H ⁶ : CS → CL	00.708	7.559 [^]	Confirmed
H ⁷ : CRM → CL	00.145	3.055 [^]	Confirmed

Note: ^ Indicates significance at $p < 0.05$

Source: Author's own compilation.

Table 7's results provide enhanced insights into the connections among the variables.

Hypothesis H1, which proposed that Service Quality (SQ) significantly influences Customer Satisfaction, received confirmation. The standardized path coefficient for this relationship was 0.241, indicating that improvements in Service Quality (SQ) indeed lead to enhanced customer satisfaction. This finding aligns with prior research, including that by (Ahmed, Huma, and Ikram 2019b), who underscored the importance of logistics service quality in fostering satisfaction within Hyderabad, Pakistan's courier industry.

Hypothesis H2 demonstrates that perceived value (PV) significantly impacts customer satisfaction, as indicated by a standard coefficient value of 0.187. This result reflects findings by (Ramaj and Ismaili 2015), who noted that perceived value positively influences customer satisfaction in Hyderabad, Pakistan's e-commerce logistics sector.

Hypothesis H3 highlights the significant impact of BI (brand image) on customer satisfaction, evidenced by a standard coefficient of 0.227. This finding is consistent with the study by (Hussain et al. 2023b), which concluded that a robust brand image positively influences customer satisfaction and purchasing intent within Hyderabad, Pakistan's logistics industry.

Hypothesis H4 confirms that customer relationship management (CRM) significantly influences satisfaction, as indicated by a standard coefficient of 0.199. This aligns with findings from (Khan et al. 2023), whose research on CRM practices in Hyderabad, Pakistan, demonstrated their role in cultivating enduring trust and commitment, thereby enhancing customer satisfaction through the development of more robust customer relationships.

Hypothesis H5 indicates that trust (T) significantly impacts customer satisfaction, a relationship supported by a standard coefficient value of 0.283. This aligns with prior research, such as that by (Khan et al. 2023), which underscored trust's crucial function in e-commerce logistics for both guaranteeing customer satisfaction and cultivating enduring loyalty.

Hypothesis H6 supports that customer satisfaction (CS) strongly impacts customer loyalty (CL), with a standard coefficient of 0.708. The results align with the conclusions of (Naveed et al. 2022), who found that customer satisfaction drives loyalty in Hyderabad, Pakistan's courier services and logistics.

Hypothesis H7 reveals that customer relationship management (CRM) positively influences loyalty, supported by a standard coefficient value of 0.145. This result aligns with the findings of (N. Memon, Shah, and Warsi 2023b), which identified CRM as a crucial driver for enhancing customer loyalty and lifetime value in Hyderabad, Pakistan's logistics and supply chain sector.

5. Conclusion & Suggestions

5.1 Conclusion & Discussion

This research focuses on loyalty and customer satisfaction within the express delivery sector, investigating the theories and methodologies to evaluate these crucial factors. By leveraging the SERVQUAL model and hierarchical structure methods, alongside the unique characteristics of express delivery enterprises, an evaluation framework for customer satisfaction and loyalty was developed. The research methodology employed a customer questionnaire to gather primary data, ensuring both speed and relevance in

capturing customer evaluations. This approach not only provided immediate insights but also reflected the most direct customer opinions, enhancing the credibility and applicability of the findings.

The analysis included testing the reliability and validity of the data, performing Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) across multiple dimensions, and employing a Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to analyze the model's fit. The results confirmed the feasibility and effectiveness of the proposed hypotheses. Findings revealed that all five evaluated dimensions positively impact customer satisfaction, while two dimensions significantly influence customer loyalty. Among these, customer satisfaction emerged as the strongest driver of customer loyalty. Following this, customer trust in merchants, brand image, service quality, customer relationship management, and perceived value also contributed to loyalty and customer satisfaction. Finally, This research proposes actionable recommendations intended to improve loyalty and customer satisfaction within express logistics enterprises, which are critical to maintaining competitiveness and long-term growth in this industry.

5.2 Suggestions

To address the challenges of internal and external competition and strengthen market position in the express delivery industry, enhancing consumer satisfaction and loyalty is critical. Improving service quality is vital, as it serves as the primary touchpoint between customers and express delivery companies in the context of online shopping. High service quality not only directly impacts customer loyalty but also indirectly improves it through increased customer satisfaction. Express delivery companies should prioritize scientific and strategic network layouts while incorporating intelligent technological solutions such as automated delivery lockers to enhance service efficiency and reliability. Adopting advanced information technology can provide customers with accurate, real-time updates regarding order status, processing, transit, and delivery timelines. This transparency improves customers' overall shopping experience by setting clear and accurate expectations, thus positively influencing their perceived value of the service. Express delivery enterprises must focus on meeting and exceeding customer expectations by ensuring timeliness, convenience, and high-quality service standards throughout the delivery process. Special attention should be given to processes like returns and replacements, which significantly affect customer satisfaction. Additionally, a strong service recovery mechanism must be in place to swiftly address and rectify service errors, demonstrating the company's commitment to customer satisfaction.

Developing a customer-centric service culture is essential for earning and maintaining consumer trust. Enterprises should ensure their staff uphold professional standards and adopt customer-focused attitudes to foster long-term trust and loyalty. Focusing on the "last-mile" experience in express delivery can enhance the overall online shopping experience for customers. By providing exceptional service during the delivery process, enterprises can strengthen their relationship with customers, thereby fostering loyalty. This process also emphasizes the importance of customer management strategies that positively impact customer loyalty through the mechanism of satisfaction. Enterprises must also focus on building a strong corporate brand and improving their technological infrastructure. Strengthening information systems will allow for seamless logistics operations by connecting all nodes within the supply chain. Reliable and efficient communication of logistics information will ensure smooth coordination and

elevate the company's reputation in the industry.

By implementing these recommendations, express delivery companies can effectively enhance customer satisfaction, cultivate customer loyalty, and secure a competitive edge in the rapidly growing e-commerce market.

5.3 Limitation and Future Research

This research examines the elements that shape customer satisfaction and loyalty within express delivery enterprises through theoretical analysis, questionnaire design, and data processing, yielding conclusions with valuable reference points. While targeted recommendations have been proposed for express delivery enterprises, further research is required to address certain limitations.

The current research model has room for development. In the context of online shopping, consumers' perceptions of express delivery services not only shape their impressions of the logistics companies but also influence their perception of online shopping platforms and merchants. Therefore, future research could expand the model by incorporating consumers' overall perceptions of online shopping merchants and platforms. This approach would provide a more comprehensive understanding and enhance the depth of future investigations.

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